

NEWSLETTER

SPECTRO

CYBER & ROBOTICS INSIGHTS

Edition 1 | May 2026

S P E C T R O

SPECIALISED EDUCATION PROGRAMMES IN CYBERSECURITY AND ROBOTICS

Co-funded by
the European Union

WELCOME!

We are excited to launch this new space where we will share the latest updates, achievements, events, and opportunities from the SPECTRO community. In each edition, we will take you **behind the scenes of our work**, highlight key milestones, and keep you informed about events, **learning opportunities, and developments in cybersecurity and robotics education within Europe.**

“BUILD THE BETTER SECURITY SYSTEMS FOR A DIGITAL EUROPEAN FORTRESS”

Challenge: Europe is rapidly expanding innovation in cybersecurity, robotics, and autonomous systems, but there is still a shortage of professionals with expertise in secure digital infrastructures, intelligent systems, and advanced automation.

SPECTRO's response: A Digital Europe Programme initiative developing advanced education programmes to train **specialists in Cybersecurity and Robotics.**

The bigger picture: Strengthening Europe's **advanced digital skills capacity** and supporting its digital sovereignty, resilience, and competitiveness in two strategic technology fields through:

- ➔ **Two double-degree Master's programmes in Cybersecurity and Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots** (ISCED Level 7, 120 ECTS)
- ➔ **Certification-oriented self-standing modules in Cybersecurity and Robotics**
- ➔ **A connected European education ecosystem** linking higher education institutions, research centres, industry partners, and SMEs
- ➔ **Scholarship opportunities** supporting access to advanced education in strategic digital technologies

OUR CONSORTIUM

SPECTRO is coordinated by **28DIGITAL** and brings together **13** higher education institutions from **7** countries, alongside **4** innovative SMEs and a leading research centre in Information Systems, with complementary expertise to build a strong and sustainable European learning ecosystem for Cybersecurity and Robotics. Find out more about us **[HERE](#)**.

Developing a double-degree Master's programme and modular self-standing learning pathways in **Cybersecurity and Robotics**

HOW DOES THE PROGRAMME WORK

Two countries, two universities, one shared learning journey. Students begin at an **Entry University** in the first year, continue at an **Exit University** in the second year, and complete the experience with the EIT Digital Summer School in between. This international path combines academic mobility with exposure to different teaching approaches, research environments, and innovation ecosystems in Europe.

CYBERSECURITY TRACK

What does it take to protect tomorrow's digital world? Students build a strong foundation in **cybersecurity** together with **business and management**, then expand their knowledge through the **Cyber Security** common core, business development exercises, and a design project that shows how technical solutions can become real-world applications.

Where can I study Cyber Security?

Click on the image to enlarge.

AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS AND INTELLIGENT ROBOTS TRACK

How do intelligent systems move from theory into real-world use? Students build expertise in **areas such as IoT, AI, machine learning, robotics, automation, embedded systems, and system communication**, then apply it through hands-on projects, workshops, and teamwork focused on autonomous systems.

Where can I study Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots?

SELF-STANDING LEARNING MODULES

Looking to build specialised skills in a flexible way? SPECTRO's self-standing learning modules offer two focused learning strands - **Cybersecurity and Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots** - designed for learners who want to upskill, reskill, or deepen their expertise through flexible online courses that can be followed independently.

The **Cybersecurity** strand covers topics such as **cybersecurity foundations, cryptography, ethical hacking, access control, malware, privacy-enhancing technologies, offensive security, steganography, computer and network security, and quantum communication.**

SPECTRO Cybersecurity Courses

<p>15 Lessons</p> <p>Foundations of Cyber Security</p> <p>Antti Hakkala</p>			
<p>23 Lessons</p> <p>Introduction to Computer and Network Security</p> <p>Matteo Golinelli</p>			
<p>9 Lessons</p> <p>Privacy Enhancing Technologies</p> <p>Mate Gyarmati</p>			
<p>7 Lessons</p> <p>Quantum Communication and...</p> <p>Tudor Mihoc</p>			

The **Autonomous Systems and Intelligent Robots** strand covers topics such as **artificial intelligence, intelligent robots, autonomous multi-agent systems, distributed autonomous systems, computer vision, industrial robotics, software engineering, robotics for agriculture, and robotics in healthcare**

SPECTRO Robotics Courses

<p>FREE</p> <p>10 Lessons</p> <p>Introduction to Computer Vision</p> <p>Marton Szemenyei</p>			
<p>FREE</p> <p>8 Lessons</p> <p>Principles of Artificial Intelligence</p> <p>Zoltán Istenes</p>			
<p>FREE</p> <p>8 Lessons</p> <p>Robotics in Healthcare</p> <p>Veronica Campana</p>			

And that's not all: learners can work towards **Basics and Advanced Certificates** by combining selected modules with Innovation & Entrepreneurship content, completing at least 30 learning hours, and achieving a 100% quiz success rate (retakes allowed).

ARTICLE FEATURE

SPECTRO was also featured in [CyberHubs - European Network of Cybersecurity Skills Hubs](#) through the article [Closing the skills gap: how integrated Cyber Robotics expertise is becoming Europe's new gold standard](#), published on **21 November 2025**. This feature gave the project added visibility within the broader European digital skills landscape and helped underline the relevance of SPECTRO's integrated approach to cybersecurity and robotics education.

EVENT HIGHLIGHTS

Since its launch, SPECTRO has built visibility through a **broad range of activities across Europe**, creating opportunities to connect with students, researchers, and innovation communities. The project was presented at events including Aalto University's Double Degree Day, ICRAE 2025, Sophia Summit, Disarray 2025, the EIT Digital Master School Graduation, and the launch event of Today Software Magazine, (March issue, 2026) with Babeş-Bolyai University. SPECTRO was also present through activities such as Unfiltered: the truth about entrepreneurship, helping connect the project with students, researchers, and wider professional communities.

Drop-in sessions. SPECTRO was also featured during the **EIT Digital Master School** drop-in sessions held by partner institutions including **Università di Bologna, Università di Trento, Université Côte d'Azur, Babes-Bolyai University, Eötvös Loránd University, Politecnico di Torino, Politecnico di Milano** and **TalTech – Tallinn University of Technology**. These sessions created space for direct questions about the programmes, the application journey, mobility opportunities, and student experience in a more informal setting.

Webinars. Various online sessions also supported visibility around the project's educational offer. The information webinar Study Cybersecurity or Robotics with EIT Digital, held on 24 March 2026, introduced the Master's offer, study paths, and overall student experience.

LIVE Q&A

Learn about the master's programs
Autonomous Systems and Intelligent
Robots, and Cyber Security

IDEATE, ITERATE, INNOVATE.

Tuesday 24 March 2026, 17:00 CET

Viktoria Villianyi
Cybersecurity Program Lead, ELTE

Mélanie Romano
Cybersecurity Master Alumna

Lorenzo Fici
Robotics Masters Alumnus

Andrea Del Prete
Robotics Program Lead, UNITN

News from the wider field. Beyond education, the consortium also contributes to discussions shaping the digital landscape. Recent updates highlight initiatives such as ENISA's international strategy to strengthen Europe's cybersecurity ecosystem, as well as ongoing developments around the Cyber Resilience Act and its role in enhancing digital security across the EU.

WHAT NEXT?

Summer School: Looking ahead, the focus shifts to the upcoming **28DIGITAL Summer School: Cybersecurity for Dual-Use AI-Driven Robotic Innovations** in Rennes, hosted by the Université de Rennes I (29 June – 10 July), where participants will spend 2 weeks analyzing cyber threats, autonomous technologies and designing scalable solutions for civilian and defense contexts.

Recruitment. The SPECTRO journey is ongoing! **Application Period 3** is open and will close on 1 June 2026, giving you the opportunity to join a European double-degree experience in Cybersecurity and Robotics.

SECOND ROUND OF APPLICATIONS: LAST CALL

Deadline: JUNE 1ST

Earn a double master's degree in Cybersecurity and Robotics with EIT Digital Master School - combining technical excellence with a strong minor in Innovation and Entrepreneurship.

✨ Ready to take the next step? **We take pride in the results of our alumni: 92% of them are employed after graduation, with 83% securing their first role within just three months.** SPECTRO equips you with all you need to lead in the field. Don't wait, **apply** now!

SPECTRO will continue to promote its programmes, expand its visibility through events and outreach activities, and strengthen the links between education, research, and industry.

Interested in the programme or upcoming activities?

Follow us, subscribe to our newsletter and stay connected with the SPECTRO community for the latest news, events, and opportunities in cybersecurity and robotics across Europe.

Follow us

STAY TUNED FOR MORE UPDATES
FROM THE SPECTRO COMMUNITY!

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Thank you